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Heat shock transcription factors in banana: genome-wide characterization and expression profile analysis during development and stress response

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Banana (*Musa acuminata*) is one of the most popular fresh fruits. However, the rapid spread of fungal pathogen *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *cubense* (*Foc*) in tropical areas severely affected banana growth and production. Thus, it is very important to identify candidate genes involved in banana response to abiotic stress and pathogen infection, as well as the molecular mechanism and possible utilization for genetic breeding. Heat stress transcription factors (Hsfs) are widely known for their common involvement in various abiotic stresses and plant-pathogen interaction. However, no *MaHsf* has been identified in banana, as well as its possible role. In this study, genome-wide identification and further analyses of evolution, gene structure and conserved motifs showed closer relationship of them in every subgroup. The comprehensive expression profiles of *MaHsfs* revealed the tissue- and developmental stage-specific or dependent, as well as abiotic and biotic stress-responsive expressions of them. The common regulation of several *MaHsfs* by abiotic and biotic stress indicated the possible roles of them in plant stress responses. Taken together, this study extended our understanding of *MaHsf* gene family and identified some candidate *MaHsfs* with specific expression profiles, which may be used as potential candidates for genetic breeding in banana.

Plant heat shock responses are mediated by heat shock elements (HSEs, nTTCnnGAAnnTTCn), which are widely present in the upstream of the heat shock proteins (HSPs)^{1–5}. The first specific transcription regulator that is responsible for HSE binding, was characterized and confirmed as heat stress transcription factor (Hsf) in yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*)⁶. Thereafter, Hsfs act through the cis-acting element of HSE, thus directly recognize the promoters of HSPs and regulate their transcripts^{7–9}.

As evolutionarily conserved transcription factors, Hsfs have some conserved domains. (i) the highly structured N-terminal DNA-binding domain (DBD), that is responsible for binding HSEs in the promoters of several HSPs; (ii) the oligomerization domain (HR-A/B), that is connected to the DBD by a flexible linker; (iii) nuclear export signal (NES) of motif –LFGV– and nuclear localization signal (NLS), (iv) C-terminal activator motif, also known as AHA motif^{8–12}. According to the flexible linker of variable length (about 15–80 amino acids) and the oligomerization domain (HR-A/B), plant Hsfs can be divided into at least three types, including class A (A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A6, A7, A8, A9), class B (B1, B2, B3, B4) and class C (C1, C2)^{1,2,9–12}.

Plant *Hsfs* are important regulators of various plant responses to abiotic and biotic stresses, including heat, cold, salt, drought, osmotic^{12–16}, as well as bacterial and fungal pathogen infection^{17–20}. After initially identified in yeast⁶, plant *Hsf* gene family has been identified and characterized in more and more plant species, including alfalfa (*Medicago sativa* L.)²¹, *Arabidopsis thaliana*²², rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)^{23,24}, maize (*Zea mays* L.)²⁵, *Medicago*

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truncatula, *Populus trichocarpa*²⁶, wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.)²⁷, soybean (*Glycine max*)^{28,29}, Chinese cabbage (*Brassica rapa* ssp. *pekinensis*)^{10,30}, cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum*)³¹, pigeonpea (*Cajanus cajan*), barrel medic (*Medicago truncatula*)³², pepper (*Capsicum annuum* L.)^{33,34}, pear (*Pyrus bretschneideri*)³⁵, *Populus euphratica*³⁶, strawberry (*Fragaria vesca*)³⁷, tea plant (*Camellia sinensis*)³⁸, wild Chinese grapevine (*Vitis pseudoreticulata*)³⁹, etc.

Banana (*Musa acuminata*) is one of the most popular fresh fruits worldwide, and cultivated in the subtropical and tropical areas^{40–43}. To date, many banana varieties have been screen and cultivated in China. For example, BaXi jiao (*Musa acuminata* L. AAA group cv. Cavendish, BX) is widely cultivated for its high yield, long fingers and long-term storage; Fen jiao (*Musa* ABB Pisang Awak, FJ) is widely cultivated for its good flavor and good resistant to various abiotic stresses^{44,45}. However, because of the rapid spread of fungal pathogen *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *cubense* (*Foc*) in tropical areas, banana growth and production are severely affected^{46–58}. Thus, it is very important to identify candidate genes involved in banana response to both high temperature and pathogen infection, as well as the molecular mechanism and possible utilization for genetic breeding. Hsfs are widely known for their common involvement in various abiotic stresses including heat stress and plant-pathogen interaction. However, no *MaHsf* have been identified in banana, as well as their possible roles. In this study, genome-wide identification and expression analysis during development and stress response were performed to extend our understanding and possible utilization of *MaHsfs* in genetic breeding.

Results

Genome-wide identification of *Hsfs* in banana. After initial identification using *Musa acuminata* v1 Phytozome database v10.3 and Plant Transcription Factor Database (PlantTFDB) v3.0⁵⁹ as well as further confirmation using National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI)'s conserved domain database (CDD)⁶⁰ and Pfam database⁶¹, 43 *MaHsfs* were successfully obtained from banana genome (Supplementary Table S1). The amino acid residues, molecular weight (MW) and theoretical isoelectric point (pI) of 43 *MaHsf* proteins were largely different, ranging from 96 aa/10.25 kDa (*MaHsf12*) to 547 aa/60.12 kDa (*MaHsf8*), 4.48 pI (*MaHsf8*) to 11.84 pI (*MaHsf39*) (Supplementary Table S1).

Phylogenetic analysis of *MaHsfs*. To investigate the evolutionary relationship among *Hsfs* from cassava, *Arabidopsis* and rice, an un-rooted Neighbor-Joining tree was created based on the coding sequences of 43 *MaHsfs*, 22 *AtHsfs* and 25 *OsHsfs* (Fig. 1). Generally, *MaHsfs* have closer relationship with *OsHsfs* in comparison to *AtHsfs*, in accordance with the current understanding in their evolutionary history. Evolutionary analysis also identified some orthologous *Hsfs* between cassava and rice, indicating the similar roles of these genes in cassava and *Arabidopsis*.

Gene structure and conserved motif analysis of *MaHsfs*. To reveal the structural features of *MaHsfs*, intron/exon and upstream (5' UTR)/downstream (3' UTR) structures were analyzed using Gene Structure Display Server (GSDS) v2.0⁶². The numbers of intron of *MaHsfs* varied from 1 to 5 (Fig. 2). Most of *MaHsfs* (29 of 43) have no upstream and downstream sequences, only *MaHsf10* and *MaHsf11* have both upstream and downstream sequences, and 12 *MaHsfs* have only downstream sequences (Fig. 2). Moreover, *MaHsfs* in the same subfamilies exhibited similar exon-intron structure, indicating the link between evolutionary relationship and gene structure. To better understand the functional prediction of *MaHsfs*, 7 conserved motifs were identified using Multiple Em for Motif Elicitation (MEME) v4.11.0 (Fig. 3). Similarly, *MaHsfs* in the same subfamilies showed similar motifs, indicating the link between evolutionary relationship and conserved motifs.

Expression analysis of *MaHsfs* in different banana tissues. The expression levels of *MaHsfs* are important clues for their possible roles in banana growth and development, and the transcripts of *MaHsfs* in five-leaf stage leaves, roots and fruits of 80 days after flowering (DAF) were obtained by transcriptomic analysis^{44,45}. Generally, *MaHsfs* showed similar expression pattern in leaves, roots and fruits of BX and FJ varieties, with litter differences in several genes (14 of 43 genes) (*MaHsf8*, 27, 17, 4, 43, 12, 16, 21, 14, 19, 24, 20, 36, 42) (Fig. 4). The *MaHsfs* with similar expression pattern can be clearly shown in the cluster analysis (Fig. 4).

For BX varieties, (i) 16 of 43 *MaHsfs* displayed higher transcripts in five-leaf stage leaves, relative lower transcripts in roots and fruits (cluster A). (ii) 19 of 43 *MaHsfs* exhibited relative higher transcripts in roots, and 8 of 43 *MaHsfs* showed lower transcripts in fruits (cluster B).

For FJ varieties, (i) 11 of 43 *MaHsfs* displayed higher transcripts in five-leaf stage leaves, relative lower transcripts in roots or fruits (cluster A). (ii) 22 of 43 *MaHsfs* exhibited relative higher transcripts only in roots, 9 of 43 *MaHsfs* exhibited relative higher transcripts in both roots and fruits, 1 of 43 *MaHsfs* showed lower transcripts in fruits (cluster B).

Expression analysis of *MaHsfs* in different developmental stages of fruit development and ripening of banana. Besides different banana tissues, the transcripts of *MaHsfs* in different stages of fruit development (0, 20, 80 DAF) and ripening (8 and 14 days (BX) or 3 and 6 days (FJ) postharvest (DPH)) were also analyzed by transcriptomic analysis^{44,45}. Although some slight differences were exhibited, *MaHsfs* showed similar expression pattern in different stages of fruit development and ripening of BX and FJ varieties, as evidenced by the cluster analysis in the heatmap (Fig. 5). In cluster A, most of *MaHsfs* exhibited relative higher transcript accumulation in fruit development and ripening, and three *MaHsfs* (*MaHsf23*, 25, 43) showed decreased transcripts in later fruit ripening in both BX and FJ varieties (Fig. 5A). In cluster B, most of *MaHsfs* showed relative lower transcripts in fruit development and ripening in both BX and FJ varieties, while *MaHsf39* showed no significant difference in these stages of BX, 6 *MaHsfs* (*MaHsf7*, 12, 21, 22, 38, 42) displayed relative higher transcripts in fruit development and early fruit ripening (Fig. 5B).

Figure 1. The phylogenetic tree of 43 *MaHsfs*, 22 *AtHsfs* and 25 *OsHsfs* that was constructed using MEGA5.05 software.

Expression analysis of *MaHsfs* in response to cold, salt and osmotic stresses. To extend our understanding of *MaHsfs* in response to abiotic stress, the expression patterns of these genes in response to cold, salt and osmotic stresses were also revealed by transcriptomic analysis^{44,45}. Although some similar expression patterns were exhibited (cluster A, B and C), *MaHsfs* showed complex expression patterns in response to abiotic stress in BX and FJ varieties, as evidenced by the cluster analysis in the heatmap (Fig. 6).

For BX varieties, 20, 19 and 13 *MaHsfs* were regulated by cold stress (16 up-regulated genes and 4 down-regulated genes), osmotic stress (13 up-regulated genes and 6 down-regulated genes) and salt stress (5 up-regulated genes and 8 down-regulated genes), respectively (Figs 6 and 7A). Among these genes, *MaHsf31* transcript was commonly up-regulated by cold, salt and osmotic stresses, *MaHsf19* and *MaHsf36* transcripts were commonly up-regulated by cold and osmotic stresses, *MaHsf12*, 35, 39 and 43 transcripts were commonly up-regulated by salt and osmotic stresses (Figs 6 and 7A). On the contrary, *MaHsf38* transcript was commonly down-regulated by cold and salt stresses, *MaHsf20*, 21, 22, 24 and 29 transcripts were commonly down-regulated by salt and osmotic stresses (Figs 6 and 7A).

For FJ varieties, 18, 13 and 10 *MaHsfs* were regulated by cold stress (16 up-regulated genes and 2 down-regulated genes), osmotic stress (11 up-regulated genes and 2 down-regulated genes) and salt stress (7 up-regulated genes and 3 down-regulated genes), respectively (Figs 6 and 7B). Among these genes, *MaHsf21* and *MaHsf40* transcripts were commonly up-regulated by cold, salt and osmotic stresses, *MaHsf6*, 9, 18, 22 and 24 transcripts were commonly up-regulated by cold and osmotic stresses, *MaHsf16* and *MaHsf35* transcripts were commonly up-regulated by cold and salt stresses, *MaHsf20* and *MaHsf38* transcripts were commonly up-regulated by salt and osmotic stresses (Figs 6 and 7B). On the contrary, *MaHsf43* transcript was commonly down-regulated by salt and osmotic stresses (Figs 6 and 7B).

Moreover, we also found the transcripts of some *MaHsfs* were regulated by the same stress in both BX and FJ varieties (Fig. 7C–E). For cold stress, 12 *MaHsfs* (*MaHsf5*, 6, 8, 9, 18, 19, 21, 22, 24, 25, 29, 31) transcripts were

Figure 2. Gene structure analysis of 43 *MaHsfs*. The relationship of gene evolution and structure was analyzed using MEGA5.05 and GSDS v2.0.

Figure 3. The conserved motif analysis of 43 *MaHsfs*. The relationship of gene evolution and motifs was analyzed using MEGA5.05 and MEME v4.11.0.

Figure 4. Gene expression heatmap of *MaHsfs* in banana leaves, roots and fruits. The samples of different banana organs were harvested from five-leaf stage leaves, roots and fruits of 80 DAF as Hu *et al.* (2015b,c) described. The heatmap was constructed using CLUSTER software and Java Treeview software.

up-regulated in both BX and FJ varieties (Fig. 7C). For osmotic stress, *MaHsf36* transcript was up-regulated in both BX and FJ varieties (Fig. 7D). For salt stress, *MaHsf35* transcript was up-regulated, *MaHsf24* and *MaHsf29* transcripts were down-regulated in both BX and FJ varieties (Fig. 7E).

Identification of several *MaHsfs* responsive to *Foc1* and *Foc4* inoculation. The rapid spread of fungal pathogen *Foc* in tropical areas severely affects banana growth and production^{46–58}. To investigate the possible involvement and utilization of *MaHsfs* in plant-pathogen interaction, the transcriptomic analysis of banana roots in response to control, *Foc1* or *Foc4* were also obtained⁵⁰. Totally, 12 of 43 *MaHsfs* were significantly regulated by *Foc* infection (Fig. 8). Among these genes, 5 *MaHsfs* (*MaHsf3*, 17, 20, 24, 41) were commonly up-regulated by *Foc1* and *Foc4*, 2 *MaHsfs* (*MaHsf31*, 35) were commonly down-regulated by *Foc1* and *Foc4* (Fig. 8). *MaHsf1* and *MaHsf6* were first up-regulated and later down-regulated by *Foc1* and *Foc4*, whereas *MaHsf2* and *MaHsf4* were down-regulated by *Foc1*, but were up-regulated by *Foc4* (Fig. 8).

Discussion

As one of the most popular fresh fruits worldwide, banana are severally destroyed by various abiotic stress (cold, salt, drought, etc) and biotic stress (especially the fungal pathogen *Foc* infection) during growth and developmental stages^{46–58}. To solve these questions, the farmers and researchers have increased the planting area and improved cultivated technique, however, the effect is very limited. Because no strong stress-resistant banana variety can be used, it is essential to construct new stress-resistant variety through genetic and molecular breeding^{46–55}. Considering the common involvement of *Hsfs* in plant stress responses, *MaHsfs* were chosen for analyzed as candidate genes for further utilization in genetic breeding.

Generally, 43 *MaHsfs* were genome-wide identified and the phylogenetic evolution of these genes was also revealed. Based on the data of RNA-seq^{44,45,50}, the comprehensive expression profiles of 43 *MaHsfs* were revealed.

Figure 5. Gene expression heatmap of *MaHsfs* in different developmental stages. The samples of different stages of fruit development and ripening were harvested from fruits of 0, 20, 80 DAF, 8 and 14 days (BX) or 3 and 6 days (FJ) DPH as Hu *et al.* (2015b,c) described. The heatmap was constructed using CLUSTER software and Java Treeview software.

To our knowledge, this is the first study extending our understanding of *MaHsf* gene family. Generally, the expression profiles can be divided to two sections. One is the expression of 43 *MaHsfs* at developmental stages, or different tissues, this is the basic information of this gene family. We found that the transcripts of some *MaHsfs* are tissue- and developmental stage-specific or dependent, indicating the possible roles of them in specific growth or developmental stages, such as fruit ripening. The other one gene expression in response to various abiotic and biotic stresses, which intends to identify several candidate genes commonly regulated by various stresses for stress-related genetic breeding.

In this study, multiple of abiotic and biotic stress-responsive *MaHsfs* were also identified, in accordance with previous studies of *Hsf* gene family in other plant species^{1–5}. Based on the clues from transcript pattern, the *in vivo* roles of several plant *Hsfs* have been revealed. *AtHsfA1s*, *AtHsfA2* and *AtHsfA6a* confers heat, salt and dehydration stress resistance in *Arabidopsis*^{3,5,7,8}. *OsHsFA2dI* is essential for heat stress resistance in rice¹, respectively. *AtHsfA6a* confers salt and dehydration stress resistance in *Arabidopsis*³. A seed preferential *TaHsf* confers abiotic stress tolerance in *Arabidopsis*²⁷, and overexpression of *GmHsf-24* increased drought and heat stress resistance in *Arabidopsis*²⁹. These results provide solid evidence of the protective roles of plant *Hsfs* in abiotic stress responses. In this study, 12 *MaHsfs* (12, 19, 20, 21, 22, 24, 29, 31, 35, 36, 39, 43) in BX variety and 10 *MaHsfs* (6, 9, 16, 18, 20, 22, 24, 35, 38, 43) in FJ variety were commonly regulated by at least two abiotic stresses (fold change >2), indicating their possible roles in abiotic stress. Thus, these *MaHsfs* can be further chosen for functional analysis.

Additionally, plant *Hsfs* are also involved in plant-pathogen interactions^{17–20}. The activation of *OsHsf23* is important for cell death in rice inoculated with rice blast fungus²⁰. *AtHsfA1b*, *AtHsfB1* and *AtHsfB2b* are involved in plant pathogen resistance and defense gene expression^{17,19}. Thus, the identification of 12 *Foc*-responsive *MaHsfs* (1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 17, 20, 24, 27, 31, 35, 41) may be further used as potential candidates in disease genetic breeding in

Figure 6. Gene expression heatmap of *MaHsfs* in response to cold, salt and osmotic stresses. Five-leaf stage banana seedlings were treated by 4 °C for 22 h, 300 mM NaCl for 7 d, or 200 mM Mannitol for 7 d as Hu *et al.* (2015b,c) described. The heatmap was constructed using CLUSTER software and Java Treeview software.

banana. Notably, *MaHsf31* transcript was commonly up-regulated by cold, salt and osmotic stresses in BX, and was down-regulated by *Foc 1* and *Foc 4* infection; *MaHsf20* and *MaHsf24* transcripts were commonly regulated by salt stress, osmotic stress and *Foc* infection. There are also other *MaHsfs* that are regulated by both abiotic and biotic stresses, such as *MaHsf35*. The common regulation of these *MaHsfs* by abiotic and biotic stress indicated the possible roles of them in plant stress responses, and these *MaHsfs* may be potential candidates for further functional analysis and genetic breeding in banana. We highlight the possible common involvement of four *MaHsfs* (*MaHsf20*, *MaHsf24*, *MaHsf31* and *MaHsf35*) in both abiotic and biotic stresses. It is just the beginning, further functional analysis will reveal their *in vivo* roles as well as underlying mechanism.

Taken together, this study is the first study showing *MaHsf* gene family as well as their specific expression profiles, which may be used as potential candidates for genetic breeding in banana.

Methods

Plant materials and growth conditions. Banana varieties of BX and FJ were used in this study. The five leaf stage seedlings were from Banana Tissue Culture Center (Danzhou city, Hainan province, Institute of Banana and Plantains, Chinese Academy of Tropical Agricultural Sciences). Thereafter, the seedlings were cultivated in soil in the greenhouse, which was controlled at 28 °C, with 12 h light/12 h dark cycles and 120–150 μmol quanta m⁻² s⁻¹ irradiance.

Genome-wide identification of *MaHsfs*. The candidate *MaHsfs* were first searched in *Musa acuminata* v1 (Banana) Phytozome database v10.3 (https://phytozome.jgi.doe.gov/pz/portal.html#!info?alias=Org_Macuminata) and PlantTFDB v3.0 (<http://planttfdb.cbi.pku.edu.cn/index.php>)⁵⁹. Thereafter, the candidate *MaHsfs* were further checked and confirmed using CDD (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/cdd>)⁶⁰ and Pfam database (<http://pfam.xfam.org>)⁶¹. Then the detailed information of *MaHsfs* including sequences, the locus

Figure 7. Vene diagram showing the number of overlapping *MaHsfs* that are differentially expressed under cold, salt and osmotic stresses. (A,B) Vene diagram showing the number of differentially expressed in response to cold, salt and osmotic stresses in BX variety (A) and FJ variety (B). (C–E) Vene diagram showing the number of differentially expressed in response to cold stress (C), osmotic stress (D) and salt stress (E) in both BX and FJ varieties.

Figure 8. Gene expression heatmap of *MaHsfs* in response to *Foc1* and *Foc4* inoculation. The samples were harvested from banana roots that were inoculated by control, *Foc1* or *Foc4* for 3 h, 27 h and 51 h. The heatmap was constructed using CLUSTER software and Java Treeview software.

name, chromosome location, gene and amino acid length were downloaded from *Musa acuminata v1* (Banana) Phytozome database v10.3, the MW and pI of *MaHsfs* were analyzed using ProtParam software (<http://web.expasy.org/protparam>).

Phylogenetic analysis of *MaHsfs*. Besides the coding sequences of 43 *MaHsfs*, the coding sequences of 22 *AtHsfs* and 25 *OsHsfs* were obtained from phytozome database v10.3 (<https://phytozome.jgi.doe.gov/pz/portal.html>). The phylogenetic tree of these *Hsfs* was constructed using Clustalx 1.83 software and MEGA 5.05 software by the neighbor-joining method^{63,64}.

Gene structure and conserved motif analysis of *MaHsfs*. Gene structure analysis of 43 *MaHsfs* was performed using GSDS v2.0 (<http://gsds.cbi.pku.edu.cn/index.php>) by uploading the coding sequences and genomic sequences of these genes⁶². The conserved motifs of 43 *MaHsfs* were analyzed using the MEME v4.11.0 (<http://meme-suite.org/tools/meme>) by uploading the coding sequences according to the instructions.

Expression profile analysis of *MaHsfs*. The transcriptomic data of two banana varieties (BX and FJ) in different organs, different developmental stages and in response to abiotic stress has been described in Hu *et al.*^{44,45}. Briefly, the different organs include five-leaf stage leaves, roots and fruits of 80 DAF, different developmental stages include fruits of 0, 20, 80 DAF, 8 and 14 (BX) or 3 and 6 (FJ) DPH, abiotic stress treatment include 4 °C treatment for 22 h, 300 mM NaCl treatment for 7 d and 200 mM Mannitol treatment for 7 d.

The transcriptomic data of roots in response to pathogen fungal pathogen of *Foc1* and *Foc4* has been described previously⁵⁰. For the gene expression assay, sterile tissue cultivated banana roots were inoculated by control, *Foc1* or *Foc4* for 3 h, 27 h and 51 h.

Hierarchical cluster and gene expression heatmap analysis. The hierarchical cluster analysis of gene expression was performed using CLUSTER software (<http://bonsai.hgc.jp/~mdehoon/software/cluster/software.htm>)⁶³, and the heatmap was then constructed using Java Treeview software (<http://jtreeview.sourceforge.net>)⁶⁵.

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Author Contributions

Shi H. conceived and directed this study, designed the experiments, wrote and revised the manuscript; Wei Y. performed the experiments, analyzed the data, wrote and revised the manuscript; Hu W. analyzed the data and revised the manuscript; Xia F., Zeng H., Yan Y. and Li X. performed the experiments; He C. designed the experiments and revised the manuscript. All authors approved the manuscript and the version to be published.

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